

Book Review

George B. Cummins & Yasuyuki Hiratsuka. 2003.
Illustrated Genera of Rust Fungi.

Third Edition. American Phytopathological Society, St. Paul, Minnesota. Ring leaf book. 225 pp.

The first edition of this publication (1959) was written by Dr G.B. Cummins while the second edition (1983) Dr Y. Hiratsuka was co-author, so also with the third edition.

Compared with the former edition (1983) the number of rust genera has increased from 105 to 120. The genus *Pucciniastrum* is now split in four genera, *Calyptospora*, *Naohidemyces*, *Thekopsora*, and *Pucciniastrum* while the genus *Physopella* is amalgamated with *Phakopsora*.

As in previous editions the genera are illustrated with drawings of the different spore forms, most of them made by Dr Cummins himself, in a few cases in black and white photos are also used. In addition 8 coloured plates are included, showing spore forms and symptoms.

Introduction gives an explanation of what rust fungi are, their relationship to other fungal groups, their economic importance, and the relationship between host and fungi, including Tranzschel's Law. There are also articles about collecting, identification, and preservation of material, partly with references to actual papers.

New to this edition is a key to the 13 anamorph genera, treating species previously placed in form genera, such as, e.g., *Aecidium*, *Caeoma*, and *Uredo*. They are also mentioned in the descriptions of the holomorph genera, e.g. *Uredo*-type.

Keys are also given to the 13 families of rust genera and to the genera themselves, arranged alphabetically in the families. There are three genera that these well-known uredinologists have not been able to place under families.

The greater part of the book, 140 pages out of 225, is devoted to the descriptions of the genera. In the rest of the book there are references to more general literature about rusts, to regional rust floras, and to larger papers. Finally a list of authors of the names of the rust genera and a list of technical terms are included.

The previous editions are often mentioned in reference lists which also no doubt this new one will also be.

This publication will be most valuable for beginners as well as for experienced mycologists studying this interesting order of fungi that includes about 7000 species of obligate parasites on hosts reaching from *Selaginella* and ferns to *Taraxacum* and *Hieracium*.

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